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Effect of Cognitive-Behavioral-Therapy on Attention-Deficit-Disorder among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper reports the result of a study undertaken to investigate the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) on attention deficit disorder among senior secondary students in Katsina state, Nigeria. The study, which was conducted in Katsina zonal education quality assurance of Katsina state, has two specific objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design, specifically pretest, posttest nonequivalent control groups design. Population of the study consists of 458 attention deficit disorder (212 males and 246 females) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state, a sample of 70 students (33 males and 37 females) were selected from the target population using random and purposive sampling techniques, respectively. The Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC) adapted from Edna D. Copeland (1987) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by experts and obtain 0.83 reliability coefficient using Cronbach's Alpha. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions Independent Samples t-test and ANCOVA were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that CBT is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder among the students exposed to the therapy irrespective of gender difference. Based on the findings it was concluded that CBT is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder among the students exposed to the therapy irrespective of gender difference. Consequently, it was recommended that More studies should be conducted to explore the long-term effects of cognitive behavioral therapy on attention deficit disorder in different educational settings and Further research is necessary to elucidate the differential effectiveness of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder symptoms in males and females.

Keywords: Cognitive Behavioral Therapy and Attention Deficit Disorder

Introduction

Education has a significant effect on human societies as it is the vehicle for socialization and social stratification. It is also the means by which the young ones are prepared for adult roles that will enable them to function effectively and efficiently in their living world. No society will function without adequate and proper education. According to Robert and John (2014), the progress of any nation is very much dependent on the level education of its citizens. It is perhaps in realization of this it is one of the of the philosophies of National Policy of Education (NPE) (2014) that, the duty of the states is to provide education to the citizens. Nowadays, there has been an increasing concern in the educational sector on how to ensure that students learn optimally at school so as to achieve academic excellence in their present and future lives. In Nigeria, there has been nationwide cry out on the fallen standard of education Akpan (2000). This can be attributed to the negative attitude being exhibited by the students such as inability of the students to pay attention in the classroom (Attention deficit). Some students have attention deficit disorder whereby many teachers could not use appropriate methods of handling the students. According to Aaron Beck (1967), Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) can be seen as an umbrella term generally used to refer to group of related therapies that have theoretical basis in behavior learning and cognitive psychology which are derived from scientifically proven

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theoretical models .Mindfulness based cognitive behavioral therapy, dialectical behavioral therapy, rational emotive behavioral therapy , acceptance and commitment behavioral therapy are expected or assumed to be the treatments of choice for various behavioral problems such as mood disorders, anxiety disorders, personality disorders, eating disorders, substance abuse disorders, and psychotic disorders in which attention deficit disorder is included.

Attention deficit disorder also known as Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) is a neuro developmental disorder, which many recognize as a childhood disorder (Rosler, 2010). However, a review of the literature as well as longitudinal studies of individuals with Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) reveals that symptoms persist from early childhood to adulthood (faraone, 2006; Davidson 2008). Many children with attention deficit disorder show signs of the disorder before they reach school age. But it is in school, when they are having trouble meeting expectations for kids in their grades that most are referred for diagnosis. A child who cannot pay attention at home, a child who seem to be absent minded to parents' command, a child who cannot sit still in the classroom, who blow out answers in class without raising his hands, who does not finish homework, who seems to be day dreaming when teachers give instructions are well known symptoms of attention deficit disorder. However, these are also behaviors that can be a result of other factors, from anxiety to trauma.

It was observed by the researcher that the causes of attention deficit among secondary students of Katsina zone can be due to chronic anxiety, family situation, bullying, frustration due to dyslexia and unsatisfied need. That is why it is important for the teachers especially psychology teachers to be aware of what attention deficit disorder looks like and how it influences children's behaviors and how teachers can help them succeed in school and other parts of their lives. This research is therefore intended to experiment the subject in order to observe whether the use of dialectical behavioral therapy is effective in aggression symptoms among secondary school students in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

Attention deficit disorder also known as Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) is a neuro developmental disorder, which many recognize as a childhood disorder (Rosler, 2010). However, a review of the literature as well as longitudinal studies of individuals with Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) reveals that symptoms persist from early childhood to adulthood (faraone, 2006; Davidson 2008). Many children with attention deficit disorder show signs of the disorder before they reach school age. But it is in school, when they are having trouble meeting expectations for kids in their grades that most are referred for diagnosis. A child who cannot pay attention at home, a child who seem to be absent minded to parents' command, a child who cannot sit still in the classroom, who blow out answers in class without raising his hands, who does not finish homework, who seems to be day dreaming when teachers give instructions are well known symptoms of attention deficit disorder. However, these are also behaviors that can be a result of other factors, from anxiety to trauma. It was observed by the researcher that the causes of attention deficit among secondary students of Katsina zone can be due to chronic anxiety, family situation, bullying, frustration due to dyslexia and unsatisfied need. That is why it is important for the teachers especially psychology teachers. to be aware of what attention deficit disorder looks like and how it influences children's behaviors and how teachers can help them succeed in school and other parts of their lives.

Attention deficit is very common among student's especially senior secondary students which has been affecting their school outcomes negatively. This cause worries among teachers, parents and government. Students makes careless mistakes in school work, over looks details, get easily distracted, has difficulty in following instructions, doesn't seem to be listening when spoken to directly, has trouble organizing tasks, often fails to finish work in school or chores in classroom, often avoid or resist tasks that require sustained mental effort and often losses homework and assignments. This made the teacher's think of to make students attentive in the classroom. What function the school has to play in changing their students to desired direction. Over the years, educators and psychologist have opposed the use of corporal punishment, permanent suspension and use of local therapies (example: kneeling down, canning, standing on chair and raising one leg, kneeling and facing the wall, picking a pin, carrying stones, extra work around the school, time-out or being sent out of class, detention etc.) and replace them with more sublime strategies for curbing attention deficit disorder. They believe that, harsh and extreme strategies increase attention deficit disorder rather than subduing it. Also, educators and psychologist have opposed the use of punishment and negative reinforcement. They suggest the use of more suitable strategies in controlling attention deficit. They believe that punishment and negative reinforcement increase the problem rather than eliminating it. Nowadays, Cognitive behavioral therapy (which include; mindfulness based, dialectical, rational emotive, acceptance & commitment behavioral therapy) are the most extensively researched psychotherapeutic modalities which is being used in various behavior disorders such as, dysfunctional emotions, mood disorders, behavior disorders, anxiety disorders. This gives more advantage in reducing or even eliminating such undesirable behavior than punishment and negative reinforcement used before.

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Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of CBT (CBT) on attention deficit disorder among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State. The following specific objectives are set to:

1. investigate the difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State,
2. find out the difference between the mean scores of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions are presented to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?
2. What is the difference between the mean score of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean score of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Methodology

The research adopted the quasi-experimental design of the pretest posttest nonequivalent control groups type. Both experimental group and control group were given the same pretest. The experimental group were treated with dialectical CBT for a period of four weeks while the control group were not treated. After four weeks all groups were given the same posttest. The study was undertaken in Katsina state in the northern part of Nigeria. The study was undertaken in Katsina state zonal quality assurance (latitudes 11°07'49N and 13°22'57N, longitudes of 6°52'03E and 9°9'02E) including three local government Areas (i.e Jibia, Kaita, and Katsina) in the northern part of Nigeria. At the time of the study there are 20 public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state, having population of 458 attention deficit disorder (212 males and 246 females) students, a sample of 70 attention deficit disorder (33 males and 37 females) were selected using random and purposive sampling techniques.

Two instruments, Attention deficit identification questionnaire and Adapted Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC). Attention deficit identification questionnaire which is used to identify students with attention deficit disorder is a SNAP-IV questionnaire developed by Swanson, Nolan and Pelham in 1992. It contains 26 questions divided into three subsets (inattention, hyperactivity/impulsivity and opposition/defiance) which is scored using a rating scale 0 to 3 (not at all=0, just a little=1, quite a bit=2 and very much=3). Adapted Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC) is a 54 items checklist containing information related to adolescent psycho/behavioral status which was used as the basis for categorizing the level of Attention deficit disorder Scores between 35-49% suggest mild to moderate difficulties, Scores between 50-69% suggest moderate to severe difficulties. Scores above 70% suggest major. Adapted Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC) was used as pretest and posttest. The two instruments were validated by experts and the reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha for an internal consistency of the items. The reliability coefficient of the SNAP-IV obtained a score of 0.88 while the reliability coefficient of the CADC obtained a score of 0.83. The data collection process began with the pretest administration to both experimental and control groups. This was to establish equivalence in performance between the groups before treatment. At the completion of the treatment, the posttest was administered to measure the group's performance. Data analyses of the responses collected were undertaken using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, standard error of mean and mean differences was employed to answer research questions while t-test and ANCOVA were the inferential statistics used to test the hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

Attention deficit disorder of the senior secondary students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT

Research question 1

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What is the difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?

Table 1.

Mean, standard deviation and standard error of the mean of experimental and control groups students' attention deficit disorder (ADD) scores

Variable	Group	N	M	SD	SEM	MD
ADD	Experimental	37	100.00	6.324	1.043	- 11.67
	Control	33	111.67	4.852	.845	

Table 4.1 shows that the difference between the mean score of attention deficit of students exposed to CBT (M = 100.00, SD = 6.324) and those not exposed to CBT (M = 111.67, SD = 4.852) among the senior secondary school students was -11.67 in favor the students exposed to CBT.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Table 2.

Summary of ANCOVA statistics on the mean scores of attention deficit of students in the experimental and control group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2992.068 ^a	2	1496.034	63.302	.000	.654
Intercept	137.332	1	137.332	5.811	.019	.080
Pretest ADD	617.901	1	617.901	26.145	.000	.281
Group	2473.096	1	2473.096	104.644	.000	.610
Error	1583.432	67	23.633			
Total	783693.000	70				
Corrected Total	4575.500	69				

a. R Squared = .654 (Adjusted R Squared = .644)

The table shows that the difference between the mean scores of the experimental (i.e., students with ADD exposed to CBT) (M = 100.00, SD = 6.324) and control (i.e., students with ADD not exposed to CBT) (M = 111.67, SD = 4.852) groups is significant, (F(1, 69) = 104.644, p < .05, partial eta square = .610). The partial eta squared for the group variable indicates that approximately 61.0% of the variance in post-test attention deficit scores was explained by the group differences. Given these findings, the null hypothesis is thus rejected.

Attention deficit disorder scores of the male and female senior secondary students exposed to CBT

Research question 2

What is the difference between the mean score of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?

Table 3.

Mean, Standard Deviations and Standard Error of the Mean of Attention Deficit Disorder Scores of the Experimental Group based on Gender

Variable	Gender	N	M	SD	SEM	MD
ADD	Male	18	100.22	5.600	1.320	0.43
	Female	19	99.79	7.123	1.634	

Table 4.2 shows that the difference between the mean ADD scores of the male (M = 100.22, SD = 5.600) and female (M = 99.79, SD = 7.123) students exposed to cognitive behavioral therapy among senior secondary school students is 0.43 in favor the female students.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean score of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

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Table 4.

Summary of t-test statistics on the differences between the male and female students attention deficit score in the experimental group

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	Df	T	P	Decision
ADD	Male	32	105.03	7.660	1.334	68	-0.439	.922	H ₀₂ Retained
Posttest	Female	38	105.89	8.611	1.397				

The table shows that differences between the ADD scores of the male (M =105.03, SD = 7.660) and female (M=105.89, SD =8.611) students in the experimental group (i.e., students with ADD exposed to CBT) is not significant, (t(68) = -0.439 , p = .922). Consequently, H₀₂ is retained.

Discussion of Findings

Concerning the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder among students, the finding of the study reveals that cognitive behavioral therapy is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder. This result is in agreement with the finding of Hoffman et al. (2012) who emphasized that Cognitive behavioral therapy is effective for disorders involving attention deficit disorder. This resonates with the current study's findings, where students in the experimental group displayed lower Attention deficit scores post-treatment compared to the control group. Similarly, Hollon and Beck (2016) affirmed that Cognitive behavioral therapy's focus on altering cognitive distortions aids in improving attention and executive functioning, suggesting that the intervention directly addresses deficits in attention, which aligns with the results of this study. Moreover, Sahil Ahmad (2018) in his review found that Cognitive behavioral therapy's effect on attention deficit disorder.

Also, the findings contradict that of, Faraone and Biederman mentioned in the review of Muller et al (2018) which found that Cognitive behavioral therapy is ineffective in managing attention deficit hyperactivity disorder /attention deficit disorder in children and adolescents, advocating for a combined approach with medication. While the current study demonstrates that Cognitive behavioral therapy significantly reduced attention deficit disorder symptoms, the long-term sustainability of these effects in the absence of medication could warrant further investigation. This contrast highlights the complexity of managing attention deficit disorder, suggesting that while Cognitive behavioral therapy is effective, a multi-modal treatment might be necessary for some cases.

Concerning the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder in both male and female students, the finding of the study reveals that cognitive behavioral therapy is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder in both male and female students. The finding contradicts with that of Hasson and Fine (2012) which noted that boys with attention deficit disorder benefit more from Cognitive behavioral therapy, given their tendency toward externalizing behaviors. This contrast may suggest that, while gender-specific differences in behavior exist, the structure of Cognitive behavioral therapy is robust enough to address these differences effectively. Also, the findings contradict that of Ruggiero et al. (2018) found that female students benefit more from Cognitive behavioral therapy's focus on emotional regulation, especially given that girls exhibit internalizing behaviors, such as anxiety or depression, that can accompany attention deficit disorder or aggression. While the current study found no significant gender differences, the broader literature suggests that Cognitive behavioral therapy may address different aspects of behavior in males and females, though the overall effectiveness remains consistent across genders.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is an effective intervention for reducing attention deficit disorder (ADD) among senior secondary school students in Katsina State. The results demonstrated a significant improvement in students' ability to manage their attention disorder symptoms after exposure to Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. Notably, all genders showed a more substantial reduction in attention deficit disorder symptoms. Furthermore, the study highlighted that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy is a valuable tool for addressing psychological challenges in the educational context. Its efficacy in modifying negative thought patterns and promoting emotional regulation underscores its importance as a preventive and rehabilitative strategy for behavioral disorders like attention deficit disorder. The findings suggest that

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incorporating Cognitive Behavioral Therapy into student support services and classroom management strategies could enhance the overall learning environment and improve academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. More studies should be conducted to explore the long-term effects of cognitive behavioral therapy on attention deficit disorder in different educational settings.
2. Further research is necessary to elucidate the differential effectiveness of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder symptoms in males and females.

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